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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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METHODS OF FORMING THE READINESS OF STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES FOR LESSONS USING AN INDIVIDUAL APPROACH

Kuzieva Gulnoza Makhamadaliyeva

Independent researcher at Namangan state university

Abstract: The article examines methods for forming lesson readiness in students with disabilities through an individual approach. This approach is aimed at enhancing students' knowledge, skills, and social development while taking their individual abilities into account. The study presents effective methods and practical examples, including a differentiated approach, gradual development, motivation and support, flexibility, as well as visual and interactive teaching methods. Based on the example of third-grade students, the findings demonstrate that applying an individual approach makes the lesson process more engaging, interactive, and effective.

Key words: students with disabilities, individual approach, lesson readiness, differentiated approach, gradual development, motivation and support, flexibility.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada imkoniyati cheklangan o'quvchilarning darsga tayyorgarligini individual yondashuv asosida shakllantirish usullari ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Ushbu yondashuv o'quvchilarning individual qobiliyatlarini hisobga olgan holda ularning bilim, ko'nikma va ijtimoiy rivojlanish darajasini oshirishga qaratilgan. Tadqiqotda differensial yondashuv, bosqichma-bosqich rivojlantirish, rag'batlantirish va qo'llab-quvvatlash, moslashuvchanlik, shuningdek, vizual va interaktiv metodlardan foydalanishning samaradorligi yoritilgan. 3-sinf o'quvchilari misolida individual yondashuvni qo'llash dars jarayonining qiziqarli, interaktiv va samarali bo'lishiga xizmat qilishi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: imkoniyati cheklangan o'quvchilar, individual yondashuv, darsga tayyorgarlik, differensial yondashuv, bosqichma-bosqich rivojlantirish, rag'batlantirish va qo'llab-quvvatlash, moslashuvchanlik.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются методы формирования готовности учащихся с ограниченными возможностями к уроку на основе индивидуального подхода. Данный подход направлен на повышение уровня знаний, умений и социального развития учащихся с учетом их индивидуальных способностей. В работе представлены эффективные методы и практические примеры, включая дифференцированный подход, поэтапное развитие, мотивацию и поддержку, гибкость, а также визуальные и интерактивные методы обучения. На примере учащихся 3-го класса показано, что применение индивидуального подхода способствует повышению интереса, интерактивности и эффективности учебного процесса.

Ключевые слова: учащиеся с ограниченными возможностями, индивидуальный подход, готовность к уроку, дифференцированный подход, поэтапное развитие, мотивация и поддержка, гибкость.

INTRODUCTION

Taking into account the individual characteristics of each student in the educational process and developing their abilities to the maximum is one of the main tasks of today. An individual approach is especially effective when working with students with disabilities. Through this approach, students not only prepare for lessons but also gain opportunities to work independently and develop social skills.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature cited in the article includes theoretical and practical sources on the individual approach and methods of developing students with disabilities.

Abdullaeva's work *Special Education Methodology* provides a detailed description of pedagogical approaches and methods used in the special education system, which serves as the theoretical basis for this article [1, p. 12].

Mirzaev's work *Fundamentals of an Individual Approach* offers important recommendations on the principles of considering students' individual characteristics and their practical application [2, p. 23].

Karimova's research focuses on methods for developing the knowledge and skills of students with disabilities, thereby reinforcing the practical recommendations presented in this article. The Special Education Standards issued by the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation serve as an official regulatory and legal framework for ensuring the quality of education and implementing an individual approach [3, p. 45].

Overall, the analyzed literature provides a solid scientific foundation for the methods presented in the article, such as the differentiated approach, gradual development, motivation, and flexibility. At the same time, it demonstrates theoretical and practical ways to effectively implement an individual approach, illustrated through the example of 3rd-grade students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The development of creativity serves to solve a number of pedagogical tasks, including increasing teachers' professional flexibility, enriching the content of music lessons, forming students' aesthetic taste, and enhancing the emotional impact of the educational process. Therefore, creativity should be considered an integral component of the professional competence of a future music teacher.

An educational environment that provides students with opportunities to freely express their opinions and take initiative plays a significant role in the formation of creative thinking. Under such conditions, students can openly express ideas and engage in practical experimentation. Innovative and interactive educational technologies are particularly effective in developing creativity in future music teachers. Specifically, problem-based learning, project-based learning, brainstorming and cluster methods, musical improvisation exercises, and integrative activities have proven to be effective [4, p. 44].

These methods activate students' independent and creative thinking. Internal motivation acts as the main driving force of creative activity, increasing students' interest in the creative process. Reflection enables students to analyze their own work, identify mistakes, and make necessary corrections. In music education, a creative approach is most effectively implemented through practical exercises. Such activities allow students to test creative ideas and gain practical experience. During performance, internal motivation encourages students to master new technical and expressive techniques, while reflection helps them evaluate their skills and identify areas for further development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The study and application of effective methods based on an individual approach in the case of 3rd-grade students are important for ensuring the quality and convenience of the educational process. The quality of education directly depends on the level of students' development and preparedness and is determined by teachers' qualifications and the extent to which innovative methods are applied.

The Essence of an Individual Approach to Students with Disabilities. An individual approach refers to an educational process adapted to the abilities, level of development, interests, and needs of each student. In working with students with disabilities, this approach is implemented through the following principles.

A differentiated approach is a method of adapting lesson content and tasks within the educational process while considering each student's individual characteristics, ability level, and educational needs. This approach makes it possible to achieve effective results even when students differ in their level of knowledge, learning speed, and attention span [5, p. 19].

Basic principles:

1. Personalization: providing each student with tasks appropriate to their abilities.
2. Adaptability: modifying lesson activities according to students' abilities.
3. Motivation: encouraging students through achievements.
4. Monitoring and evaluation: regularly monitoring each student's learning level and adjusting lessons based on the results.
5. Practical example: Instead of assigning identical tasks to all 3rd-grade students in a mathematics lesson, stronger students are given more complex problems, while weaker students receive simpler, step-by-step exercises. In this way, each student can achieve success at their own level and increase motivation during the lesson.

Step-by-Step Development. Step-by-step development is a method of strengthening students' knowledge and skills through gradual progression. For students with disabilities, presenting new material all at once may cause fatigue or misunderstanding. Therefore, each topic or skill is taught in small, manageable steps.

Basic principles:

1. Step-by-step explanation: each topic or task is presented from simple to complex.
2. Inter-stage reinforcement: at the end of each stage, students complete practical exercises to reinforce acquired knowledge.
3. Continuous control: students' understanding is checked at each stage, and additional explanations are provided if necessary.
4. Adaptation: the interval and complexity of stages are adjusted according to students' abilities [6, p. 10].
5. Practical example: When teaching the topic Addition and Subtraction in a mathematics lesson:
 - *Stage 1:* learning to add and subtract numbers from 1–5.
 - *Stage 2:* completing exercises with numbers from 6–10.
 - *Stage 3:* solving problems involving numbers greater than 10 and practical tasks.

Through this approach, students are gradually prepared to solve more complex problems and consolidate the topic.

Advantages:

1. Students are not overburdened and absorb knowledge more effectively.
2. A sense of success is formed during the learning process, which increases motivation.
3. Complex topics become easier and more understandable.

Motivation and Support. Motivation and support represent a pedagogical approach aimed at ensuring students' active participation in the learning process, increasing motivation, and developing self-development skills. For students with disabilities, motivation plays a crucial role in maintaining interest in learning and consolidating knowledge [7, p. 31].

Basic principles:

1. Positive reinforcement: praising, encouraging, or providing small rewards for success.
2. Continuous support: offering help and explanations when students experience difficulties.
3. Personalized approach: selecting reinforcement methods appropriate to each student's characteristics and ability level.
4. Creating a positive environment: allowing students to make mistakes without fear and express their opinions freely [8, p. 5].

Practical examples:

1. Giving a small sticker or point to a student who answers correctly in mathematics.
2. Praising a student in front of the group for correct pronunciation in English.
3. Rewarding a student who successfully completes a project in social studies within a group.

Advantages:

1. Develops students' self-assessment and independent work skills.
2. Increases interest and engagement during lessons.
3. Creates a positive atmosphere and a sense of trust, which improves students' emotional well-being.

Tip: Encouragement should always correspond to the student's effort and performance. A balanced combination of constructive criticism and praise enhances lesson effectiveness [9, p. 54].

Flexibility. Flexibility refers to the ability to adapt lesson content, methods, and pace in the pedagogical process according to students' individual characteristics, abilities, and needs. When working with students with disabilities, flexibility is essential for facilitating lesson comprehension and ensuring success.

Basic principles:

1. Adaptation to individual level: modifying tasks according to each student's abilities.
2. Adaptation to learning speed: considering that some students learn faster while others require more time.

3. Adaptation of methods and techniques: identifying the methods through which each student learns most effectively.
4. Adaptation of the environment: creating comfortable learning conditions (sound, lighting, seating, etc.).

Practical examples:

1. Presenting complex mathematical problems in stages according to difficulty level.
2. Using pictures or flashcards in language lessons for students who learn better visually.
3. Assigning specific roles to active and less-active students during group work.

Advantages:

1. Lessons adapted to students' abilities increase effectiveness.
2. Students' self-confidence is enhanced.
3. Stress and fatigue are reduced, making the learning process more comfortable.

Tip: To ensure flexibility, teachers should regularly monitor students' abilities and consider individual needs in each lesson.

Methods for Developing Lesson Preparation. Use of visual materials. Visual aids help students better understand lesson content. Colorful diagrams, pictures, tables, and graphs make lessons engaging and memorable. For example, using colored blocks in mathematics allows students to grasp abstract concepts practically.

Audio and interactive methods. The use of audiovisual materials (audio-books, songs, interactive programs) helps maintain students' attention. At the same time, games and interactive activities encourage active participation. For instance, learning vocabulary through interactive cards in English lessons is effective [10, p. 12].

Practical exercises and games. Practical tasks and educational games enable students to master subjects more quickly and effectively. For example, in natural science lessons, students classify plants and animals through game-based activities, which increases interest and liveliness.

Individual lessons. Identifying each student's strengths and weaknesses and assigning individualized tasks is essential. Additional mathematics exercises or specialized reading assignments foster self-development skills [11, p. 32].

Formation of social skills. Creating opportunities for cooperation and communication during group activities is crucial for social development. Through group projects and collaborative games, students learn to communicate effectively with peers.

Examples and Practical Recommendations. The following recommendations can be applied to 3rd-grade students:

1. Develop an individual curriculum for each student.
2. Use visual and interactive materials extensively.
3. Integrate practical exercises into the main part of the lesson.
4. Organize group work to develop social skills.
5. Consistently encourage students' achievements.

Pedagogical Recommendations [12, p. 6]

Teachers are encouraged to apply differentiated assignments, use audiovisual resources, combine group and individual lessons, introduce incentive systems, and develop assessment methods tailored to each student's abilities.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Implementing an individual approach for students with disabilities significantly enhances the effectiveness of the educational process. Principles such as differentiation, gradual development, encouragement and support, and flexibility play a vital role in forming students' readiness for lessons and strengthening their knowledge and skills. Through this approach, students not only master subject content more effectively but also develop independent work skills, social competencies, and self-assessment abilities.

In the case of 3rd-grade students, applying individual approach methods makes lessons more engaging, interactive, and effective, while increasing motivation. For teachers, the systematic and accurate implemen-

tation of an individual approach is a key factor in improving educational quality, fully revealing each student's potential, and adapting lesson processes. Continuous updating of lesson plans, methodological materials, and assessment methods ensures the successful inclusion and achievement of students with disabilities. Overall, an individual approach represents an effective educational mechanism that enhances students' development, increases lesson engagement, and maximizes their potential.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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